

DIFFERENCES AND ADVANTAGES OF NEW METHODS TO SPEAK THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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“Tillarni o’qitish kafedrası” ingliz tili fani o’qituvchisi

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Annotation: This article pays great attention to the methods of teaching as well as learning how to speak the English language and written according to new technologies.

Keywords: methods of teaching, English language and written according to new technologies, frequently used words in a foreign language.

Аннотация: в данной статье большое внимание уделяется методам обучения, а также обучению говорить на английском языке и писать по новым технологиям.

Ключевые слова: методика обучения, английский язык и письменность по новым технологиям, часто употребляемые слова на иностранном языке.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o’qitish usullariga, shuningdek, yangi texnologiyalar yordamida ingliz tilida gapirish va yozishni o’rganishga katta e’tibor qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: o'qitish usullari, ingliz tili va yangi texnologiyalar asosidagi yozuv, chet tilida tez-tez ishlatiladigan so'zlar.

All differences and advantages of new methods described widely and exactly in this article and the teacher tries to give samples from his experience, which are considered very important for both teachers and learners.

1. Use simple vocabulary. Mostly try to start by learning simple and frequently used words in a foreign language: To learn a language, you should first memorize words that are more valuable and focus on using them in one’s daily speech faster and elaborately. Things needed in everyday life (family, father, mother) (house, room, wall) and other things. Teachers sometimes use such words in the course of the lesson, they are hardly required in everyday life (a part-time job, a full-time job) time to time only drilled during the unique lesson the above- mentioned words are likely to be vanished from the student's memory, and as a result, the training turns out to be very ineffective. In this case teacher’s being aware of one’s students’ background might play a crucial role on conducting fruitful lesson undoubtedly. As a sample someone may have grown up in a remote county or in a suburban backyard and these circumstances ought to leave essential tracks on their outlook.

On the one hand, Akbar is a student who comes from a distant district with the lack of some urban merits: the words heating system, a tap, a balcony are words that are scarcely used or somehow fresh item to his mindset. On the other hand, for Asror, who grew up in the city center: field, cotton, farm, hay and others may seem a little unusual or strange vocabulary for his daily used one. Knowing the translation of familiar words not only leads them to grab the subject deeply but also prevents learners from feeling strange to the new studying area.

It is acknowledged as choosing the pedagogical sphere is also demanded to be aware of all data related to learners aptly. Firstly, Teacher should learn the daily activities of his students, for example, how Anvar organizes daily routine to his studying residence exactly school or lyceum (by transport, on foot), then he should encourage him to know the names of the places in the direction of arrival. This collection of information will increase the effectiveness of learning, and it will certainly be very useful if the teacher translates these words and encourages learners to use them widely. If the student can always say these words and phrases with his eyes closed and use them in his speech, he will achieve the intended goal.

In contrast to the abovementioned ideas, some relevant obstacles can appear. Firstly, students feel shy speaking English because they are afraid of making mistakes. It usually seems at the initial level, as they are afraid of criticizing by teachers and other students. In that case, the teacher should create a friendly atmosphere of collaboration so that students will not be afraid of admitting their mistakes and will accept criticism.

According to the psychologist's research, any motivation plays a crucial role on a single learner's behavior in the result it will show its fruitful contribution to the progressive lesson.

2. Make up simple statements. Using learned words in one's speech or a real practice also supports learners to improve their speaking skills well. Only writing repeating or other kinds of memorizing new vocabulary cannot show its effect unless they are uttered frequently. It is not secret that human being's memory is a huge store, which can comprise plethora data regardless of that all gained knowledge is easily lost if it is not practiced very often. By using in simple statements, learned words can influence gradually. For instance I choose a word "mobile phone" with several reasons (very interesting equipment, nearly everyone possess). I have a mobile phone. It is black and new. It has been arguing about the necessity of teaching or learning grammar aspects in every

lesson some scholars agree to the significance of grammar on the contrary others disagree using structured teaching in the lessons. It strikes me that, grammar ought to integrate a little bit in the process of language teaching too as it is considered as the bone of the language, comparing to the human being's organ it is hard to imagine the action without Skelton, which is fully composed with bone. As it mentioned, simple structures ought to practice with the help of vocabulary and in the result, they both will track in your one's brain too deeply to be able to reproduce in any situation without any difficulty.

In my classes, I sometimes use one method to maintain irregular verbs by using them in simple sentences according to three tenses like Present Simple, Past Simple and Present Perfect Tense.

Verb1 (Infinitive)	Verb2 (Past Indefinite)	Verb3 (Participle 2)
send	sent	sent
write	wrote	written

Present Simple: Subject +Verb1 (usually, always, often, sometimes, seldom)

I often write to my friend. Sometimes He sends his friend a present.

Past Simple: Subject +Verb2 (yesterday, ago, last week, in 1991, during)

I wrote to my friend yesterday. Last week He sent his friend a present.

Present Perfect Tense: Subject +have/has +Verb3 (already, just, ever, never, yet)

I have just written to my friend. He has already sent his friend a present.

It will help them both improving their vocabulary and thriving sentence structuring. They try to guess some vital words by the motivation of completing the sentence and give relevant meaning.

Try to avoid translating the words from your brain; it will slow the learning process down by seeking for any word and its foreign version in one's mind. Consequently, a speaker makes pauses unintentionally while expressing ones idea during the conversation. The crucial way of getting rid of this situation is to teach them to be able to implement some expression or collocations. Isolated words never give great opportunity to the learners to achieve their target in studying the language. They ought to use some expressions automatically as teacher taught.

If teacher plans to explain the unique word "flower" it should be strengthened With the help of words or expressions, which serve to describe it.

I like flowers in my room because they are nice. Flowers are red and white.

In modern English grammar 16 tenses can be found in active and 10 tenses in the passive voice comparatively, on the contrary mostly five or six tenses are in the need of organizing mutual conversations via persons as well. They are the

followings: Present Simple, Present Continuous Tense, Past Indefinite Tense, Present Perfect Tense and Future Simple Tense. Students are required to learn these tenses deeply and have an ability to use automatically and step by step it leads them to integrate any conversation without any pauses. For instance:

Every day I come lyceum by car. It is expensive. Yesterday I came to lyceum by bus. This week I have read three interesting stories about English kingdom.

On the one hand, as it mentioned above the article, Taking care of structuring is likely to minimize learning activity, on the other hand knowing the grammar vital rules may support learners to memorize all words and can change in any shape they like. In this case teacher have to find relevant topics to enrich the students vocabulary for instance, my day it is a topic all words are used for collaborating present tense rules like get up, air the room, do morning jerks, have a shower, have a lesson or so on.

I usually get up at 6 o'clock in the morning. I clean the room and always do morning jerks in the open air.

Sometimes the topic can be chosen for improving past simple such as: Yesterday I got up at 6 o'clock. I cleaned the room and did morning jerks in the open air.

If tenses and vocabulary are implemented in the same time, it will be useful for improving students' knowledge.

3. Plan your day in English. In this case, I remember one event, which happened when I was a student and that time we were at the cotton picking having returned from the hard work all roommates were having delicious supper and our teacher asked my friend what language he chose when got up in the morning. It seemed very unusual question to answer after a small break he tried to explain the meaning of his question. As he mentioned it doesn't matter how many languages you can communicate in the world mostly the first word you are going to express always becomes in your native tongue. It is not secret that human beings' some traits are impossible to change yet it can be adapted or customized the best way to improve language studying is encourage them to think in foreign language by speaking oneself. Doing written or oral exercises, reading books or listening some music pieces is certainly useful for language learning but having ability to reproduce the gained words in one's speech or mind makes the process brilliant.

Several years ago during the lesson some texts or extract were given to learn by heart and we had to repeat them in our mind and speak voiceless, nowadays in some IELTS masters also use this method by giving ready speaking

materials to learn by heart and we may encounter students on our way somewhere whispering phrases or collocations. For preparing speaking exams applicants may get question list samples and try to answer them in their mind it is also one way of thinking in foreign language because while answering he thinks and repeats words, phrases.

As the whole text let us choose an ordinary day at work/ study. Here the student may repeat one's day in the memory. Today I have to go to institute earlier as the first lesson is scheduled at 8 o'clock in morning. Firstly, home tasks should be revised and then self-study have to be overviewed carefully. Secondly, for my next self- study data should be collected by visiting the library.

Speaking oneself seems to strange for others to meet, it is considered as a crazy in some culture but it should never jeopardize learners to go ahead. Among the students several obstacles appear

4. Think in conversation. At this stage, the learner goes on to independently apply or repeat the words and phrases he has learned. In fact, the main tool for learning a language and sharpening it is to find a partner to talk to. If you talk about a topic with a partner in a foreign language for as long as possible, it will not help the student. In this situation, during the lesson, the teacher should make wide use of this opportunity by creating short dialogues. Sometimes this opportunity may not be available to everyone, or some students may have a problem getting started with the interlocutor. The main solution to these problems is to encourage the student to answer questions on his own.

For example: It is raining too hard, isn't it? I think the bus is crowded today and it may be too difficult to go by bus.

Of course, for this situation, it does not hurt for the student to have knowledge about the questions.

In conclusion, in many ways, I think that the four methods or steps mentioned above can help the student to learn as quickly and efficiently as possible. I tried to prove based on my own experience and thinking about the example of a language teacher based on the video provided on the internet source. Experienced teachers can express their opinions through new and bright articles by reading this article and help to teach young people at the same time. I look forward to.

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